

Application of New Information Technologies in Tourism Enterprises

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Mankind has entered a stage of civilization development in which information and knowledge play a decisive role in all spheres of human activity. At the same time, information is becoming the most important factor of economic growth in modern society. Informatization as a process of transition to an information society has affected all spheres of human activity. The volume of the world information technology market is growing annually. Free access to information is becoming the most important feature of modern society. With the growth of information, society faces the problem of strengthening control over information and organizing information flow management systems in all spheres of human activity, especially in those that are entirely dependent on the information circulating in and around them.

At present, information systems play an important role in all service sectors, and the greatest effect from the implementation of these technologies is noted in catering establishments. Information in catering, the establishments of which are most often visited by tourists, is the link that binds together various clients within a single sphere – catering establishments. The most important feature of catering is that the relationship between producers and consumers is carried out through both food products, goods, and information flows. These information flows are not only flows of specific data, but also services and payments. Services such as hotel accommodation, seats on airplanes are not displayed in physical form and are not inspected at the point of sale, therefore the only guide to the availability and quality of food products is information. Consequently, the provision of reliable information and the speed of its dissemination is as important for the survival of catering establishments and other sectors of the economy that use their services as the actual provision of their services to consumers.

Currently, there are several directions for the implementation of information technologies in business within the framework of public catering: software for travel agencies, computer reservation systems, multimedia marketing systems, electronic media and others.

The predicted surge of interest in computerized booking of catering services seems to be already beginning in Uzbekistan. It is symptomatic that over the past year the number of subscribers to the global booking systems Amadeus , Worldspan , Galileo presented in our country has almost doubled. Due to the intensifying competition in the market and, as a result, the focus of catering enterprises on the technological nature of the catering services implementation process, as well as the boom of the Internet and e-commerce, we can expect further expansion of the computerized booking market in Uzbekistan. Let us consider these systems in a little more detail.

The Bek restaurant was the first of the global computer reservation systems that came to Uzbekistan in the late 90s. The restaurant's activity remains very high at present, now "Bek" serves more than 40 travel agencies with about 100 terminals. Since 2017, the system has begun to develop the areas of the Samarkand region, which has its own tourist flavor. Today, you can present the resources of the providers "Avia", "Hotels", "Auto". Now the system is available to any agents. A new option for connecting to the system via the Internet has been developed, which has significantly reduced the cost of use.

Domestic computer reservation systems were created taking into account the needs of passengers for food products, in particular, airlines and agents. But each of these systems has a rather limited field of action, there is no clear interaction between them, none of them has a full-fledged exit to the regional computer space.

In addition, some large tour operators are now creating on - line restaurant reservation systems on their servers depending on tours, accommodations, and airline and train tickets. The cost of food is included in the cost of tourist services . An interesting example of the work of an interactive tourist bureau is a system complex that includes an information retrieval system, a booking and sales system, and an electronic tourist newspaper. An important advantage is that all work is based on the Internet, i.e. there is no need to pay for connecting to the booking system and for a dedicated channel.

The creation of a representative office of catering enterprises at a travel agency on the Internet helps to organize and control the information flows of the travel agency, as well as attract clients to the services of the catering enterprise provided by the travel agency. A professional Web studio, preferably with experience in creating websites for travel agencies, creates an online representative office that meets all the customer's requirements, previously described in the technical specifications for the site. The technical specifications allow catering enterprises to control the process of creating a site and participate in the development of its design and content. After the site is created, issues of its registration, hosting, and support are resolved. The content of the site depends on the needs of the catering enterprise. A traffic control system will help to control the information flows passing through the site. The site should be advertised both with the help of advertising products of the catering enterprise and with the help of online advertising banners.

It is important not only to have a website, but also its high-quality processing, usefulness and uniqueness of the information posted on the website, and its ease of use. Let us list the main reasons for the need to create an Internet site for a travel agency:

- the need for an accessible and convenient way to convey information about the services provided and about the company to a potential client;
- the need to expand the clientele and increase sales;
- the need to maintain the company's image in the eyes of customers and competitors;
- the need to promote their products in the tourist services market;
- the need to create more favorable conditions for attracting clients to services and their subsequent acquisition.

The main problem at the current stage of development of the domestic tourism market is the complexity of timely and prompt information support of the tourism product. This creates difficulties not only for tourists when choosing a vacation spot, but also for agencies, tour operators and the accommodation facilities themselves. Companies are forced to recruit a large number of managers in different areas, tour operators do not have the opportunity to develop an adequate tourism product without having complete and objective information at their disposal, accommodation databases cannot inform about themselves, since their information is simply lost in the array of general data.

Nowadays, modern travel agencies increasingly prefer not the databases of individual tour operators, but tour search and booking systems.

Tour search engines consolidate information from many tour operators in their databases, giving the agency the opportunity to see the full picture of the market. It should be noted that search engines concentrate information not only from tour operators that have their own databases and provide agencies with the opportunity to search for tours using their search engines, but also information from tour operators that publish their offers in the form of price lists.

Search engines organize and systematize this information, providing it to the agency manager in a single, convenient form.

Search engines connect all components of a tour – price, tour program, flight and hotel information. This enables the manager, without resorting to additional sources, to immediately show the client the hotel, provide full flight information and announce the tour program – quickly and conveniently.

Search engines have implemented the ability to mark sales stops, which allows closing sales of tours for which departure or hotel accommodation is not possible.

Search engines have created convenient forms for searching tours by various combinations of parameters, including hotel services. Such systematized information is easy to use, you can quickly find everything that interests the client, and quickly answer any question.

Using tour search and booking systems facilitates quick tour search, which speeds up the customer service process, and accordingly, speeds up the movement of internal and external information flows. Booking systems allow using databases of a large number of tour operators, which is cheaper than using the services of all tour operators directly. These systems allow for a complete and quick analysis of the tourist services market, thanks to which a travel agency can receive information about the needs of a modern consumer of tourist services and quickly respond to changes in these needs and the market itself.

Among the information technologies currently in use, tourism industry specialists particularly highlight the Internet. After all, it is the sale of tourist services that is among the top three most active areas of electronic network commerce. And although today not every domestic company can afford to create its own virtual office, everyone can make a name for themselves on the Internet, thanks to the existence of specialized tourist sites, which are a kind of "meeting place" for tour operators, agents and their potential clients.

It is believed that e-business begins to actively push out the traditional form of trade in services when at least 35% of the population of a country has access to the Internet. According to experts, Uzbekistan will be able to cross this threshold in the near future, which makes the task of increasing its presence in the "virtual world" more relevant than ever for representatives of the domestic tourism business.

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